

Different Views and Evaluations of IT Artifacts

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Abstract : The introduction of a multitude of new and interactive e-commerce information technology (IT) artifacts has impacted adoption research. Rather than solely functioning as productivity tools, new IT artifacts assume the roles of interaction mediators and social actors. This paper describes the varying roles assumed by IT artifacts, and proposes and distinguishes between four distinct foci of how the artifacts are evaluated. It further proposes a theoretical model that maps the different views of IT artifacts to four distinct types of evaluations.

Keywords : IT adoption, IT artifacts, similarity, social actor

Conference Title : ICISOM 2014 : International Conference on Information Systems and Operations Management

Conference Location : Rome, Italy

Conference Dates : September 18-19, 2014